

HILAYA | A WELLNESS CENTER (MAIN BUILDING)

THE TERM "HILAYA," IS DERIVED FROM THE FILIPINO WORD "HILAY" WHICH MEANS TO ELEVATE OR UPLIFT, BEST CAPTURES THE INHERENT PURPOSE OF THE CENTER: TO ENHANCE THE MENTAL, PHYSICAL, AND SPIRITUAL WELL-BEING OF EACH GUEST THROUGH COMPREHENSIVE HEALING AND WELLNESS PROCESS.

THE HILAYA WELLNESS CENTER IS THE MAIN FEATURE OF THE ENTIRE RETREAT COMPLEX. IT IS DESIGNED TO BE A SANCTUARY OF SELF-DISCOVERY, HEALING THERAPIES, RECREATION AND REJUVENATION. THE ARCHITECTURAL APPROACH IS A CONTEMPORARY TROPICAL DESIGN, UTILIZING NATURAL MATERIALS, PASSIVE COOLING, AND A FLUID TRANSITION BETWEEN INTERIOR AND A SEAMLESS BLEND BETWEEN INDOOR AND OUTDOOR SPACES TO CREATE A SERENE AND MEDITATIVE ENVIRONMENT.

FRONT ELEVATION
SCALE: 1:250 MTS.

LEFT-SIDE ELEVATION
SCALE: 1:250 MTS.

REAR ELEVATION
SCALE: 1:250 MTS.

RIGHT-SIDE ELEVATION
SCALE: 1:250 MTS.

HILAYA WELLNESS CENTER (MAIN BUILDING) GROUND FLOOR PLAN
SCALE: 1:250 MTS.

FLOOR PLANS

LONGITUDINAL SECTION
SCALE: 1:300 MTS.

HILAYA WELLNESS CENTER (MAIN BUILDING) SECOND FLOOR PLAN
SCALE: 1:250 MTS.

CROSS SECTION
SCALE: 1:300 MTS.

MAIN BUILDING (FRONT VIEW)

FLOOR PLAN

MULTI-PURPOSE RESTROOM

SERVICE BUILDING

MAIN BUILDING (RIGHT-SIDE VIEW)

MAIN BUILDING (LEFT-SIDE VIEW)